

Identifying Autistic Behaviors from Video using Deep Learning and Computer Vision

Kathan Vyas^a

^a *Behavior Imaging and Biomedical Data Analytics (Boise, ID-Boston, MA)*

Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

The worldwide prevalence of children diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) has dramatically increased. Since ASD does not have clear bio markers and is a behaviorally defined disorder, a key element in the diagnostic process is direct observation of behavior and expert diagnosticians. This approach can lead to significant variability in results. However, new approaches using Artificial Intelligence (AI) are being developed that have the potential to improve the diagnostic accuracy of this process. Here, Patient videos annotated by physicians are used as input to establish a deep learning classifier that with a high accuracy to identify behavioral mannerisms for autistic patients. Each video is annotated for DSM-V classification groups and aggregated as two classes (Typical and Atypical Behavior) and the neural network

2. Aim

To achieve a confident accuracy in identifying Typical and Atypical Autistic behavioral mannerisms from tagged videos using a complex deep learning algorithm. MATERIALS AND METHODS: The videos were collected as a part of a pervious student (NODA initiative by Behavior Imaging). The individual video segments from these data are isolated and analyzed for additional features, such as motion detection as optical flow. These data are used to train both published networks (LRCN by Donahue et. al.) and newly derived networks based on similar approaches.

3. Results

6000 videos segments were preprocessed to form more 200 full patient videos. The video segments are broken down in to more than 15000 images each tagged under two classes (Typical and Atypical). These data were also used to generate optical flow measurements, that can highlight

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We used a number of approaches and algorithms and created one optimal approach that helped get the validation or test accuracies up to 82% and we aim to achieve an accuracy more than 90%.

4. Conclusions

Deep Learning algorithms work on epochs or iterations and use training-test data to get an accuracy that would help us correctly identifies the required typical characteristics for Autism. Currently the algorithm is performing above par and giving an accuracy of more than 80% and we are trying to achieve more than 90% to achieve good confidence on the algorithm. KEYWORDS: Autism, Deep Learning, Mental disorders, CNN, LSTM, GRU

Author biography

Kathan Vyas completed his Master's degree from Northeastern University in Informatics this April and is currently researching in the field of Health Informatics and Deep Learning. He has worked with a number of companies like Autodesk (San Francisco, California) and HealthPay24 (Pennsylvania) as an intern working in data analytics. It was the time when he worked with Biomedical Data Analytics in Boston he came closer to researching in deep learning and Health industry. He is a prospective PhD student concentrating in Deep Learning-Computer Vision in Personal Health Informatics. He co-founded a technological startup back in his Undergraduate days which received awards for most innovative projects and other social works.